

Redefining Scholarship

The academic community has historically deemed academic research products as the primary credible method for generating and disseminating knowledge. By terming community-generated products as “non-scholarly” or “non-academic,” even when we choose to include them in our knowledge base, we create a hierarchy and privilege the voices of academic researchers. This limits the accessibility and utility of information generated outside of academia. Factors such as technical language, proximity to academic affiliations, and the **need for journal subscriptions** hinder the reach of academic research products to those outside of universities. Additionally, valuable, peer-reviewed products generated within communities have been deemed less valid, scientific, and relevant. These factors further limit the voices of already **marginalized communities in research**.

The **RADx-UP** Program seeks to uplift and learn about those who have long been underrepresented in research as both investigators and participants. Similarly, the

RADx-UP Engagement Resource Center seeks to center the knowledge generated and disseminated by and for these underrepresented communities. In an effort to recognize these knowledge sources, “*Scholarship from the field*” or “*community scholarship*” will replace the term “non-scholarly” or “non-academic” for community-generated products. We hope to:

Expand the reach and access of scholarship centering minoritized and historically underrepresented communities

Uplift community-validated products as equally valuable to academically-validated products

Provide basic guidance for terming the various types of scholarship

Keep in Mind

How a product is categorized depends on the process by which it was created.

Definitions

Scholarship can be defined as **creative, intellectual work that is validated by peers and communicated broadly.**

Scholarship can include various forms of inquiry and result in different outcomes, but all scholarly work achieves stated goals, is documented and evaluated, and is ideally communicated or made public in appropriate ways so as to have an impact on the discipline and significance within the field.

Community scholarship, also known as “*Scholarship from the field*” is an inclusive term that centers authentic practice-based knowledge production. They are defined as research products developed by community-based organizations/leaders for the communities they serve. These products are often disseminated more quickly and directly than academic scholarship. We propose the use of the term ‘field’ to highlight that knowledge production can be a reflexive, practice-based process that centers the lived experiences of community members. As such, validity of scholarship from the field/community scholarship is determined by a peer review process comprised of collaboration and feedback from members of the community. Examples of products include dissemination materials such as briefs, reports, reference guides, data visualizations, and research tools such as **surveys**, dashboards, data tool kits; and **educational, promotional, or multimedia communication materials.**

Academic scholarship is defined as research products that require peer review by academic researchers and are published in academic journals or by academic presses.

Formal qualitative, quantitative, and/or mixed research methods are applied to determine rigor and validity of these products. Examples include academic books, book reviews, clinical case studies, research articles, and public use research data.

Community-Engaged Scholarship, also known as “*co-constructed scholarship*,” is defined as knowledge produced through a **co-learning model** between communities and academic researchers. The intent of this scholarship is for communities to lead the foundation of the knowledge production while academics serve in a logistical support role (dissemination, access, funding, implementation, etc.). As such, validation of co-constructed scholarship involves an iterative process of co-learning and bidirectional dialogue, whereby all parties contribute their expertise. Examples include co-designed surveys tools, co-authored publications, adapted infographics, **reports**, etc.

What can I do?

1. When referencing community-created products, use the terms “scholarship from the field” and “community scholarship.”
2. Incorporate community perspectives whenever appropriate and possible in research.
3. Continue the discussion! Share this information with your colleagues and partners.